

DESIGN OF CYLINDRICAL COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS: INTEGRAL OPTIMISATION

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SUMMARY

In this paper we outline an analytical method for the integral optimisation of cylindrical composite pressure vessels incorporating additional constraints like pattern consistency and strain compatibility at the cylinder dome intersection. The results reveal that designs exclusively based on shape and material parameters are in some cases far from optimal.

Keywords: *Pressure vessels, Anisotropy, Winding patterns, Stress analysis, Optimisation*

1. INTRODUCTION

The optimal design of filamentary pressure vessels (particularly cylindrical) is a wide covered topic [2, 4, 6, 8-11, 13, 16]. There are a significant number of publications dealing with structural optimisation, but the number of papers considering the effect of winding patterns is very limited [11, 14]. Another issue, insufficiently covered, is the derivation of simple design rules for strain matching at the dome cylinder intersections. As this strain mismatch, together with the resulting winding patterns, is able to overshadow the effect of structural optimisation, it is believed that an integral approach to that problem is highly desired. In other words, there is a need for a rather simple analytical model in which the roving dimensions and pattern constants are added to the classical optimisation game for pressure vessels, which typically relies only on mechanical material properties and shape parameters. The goal of this extended optimisation parameter set is to preserve the maximum the vessel performance, $(\text{pressure} \times \text{volume}) / \text{weight}$, while ensuring successful production.

As proposed in [16] the stiffness properties of the utilised composite layers are captured in a single anisotropy parameter, able to cover the entire range from isotropic materials to the netting approach. Additional design parameters are: vessel aspect ratio (maximum radius / minimum radius), cylindrical length and axial loading. To avoid bending effects, the strains of the dome and cylindrical part should match [8]. We propose here a simple strain analysis method where the set of input variables consists of the relative dome / cylinder thicknesses and the individual anisotropy parameters (as the cylindrical part is additionally covered by hoop windings).

Application of a roving with particular dimensions and strength will lead to a minimally required equatorial wall thickness, expressed as the number of closed layers, formed by a certain number of windings. This number should ideally lead to homogenous and full coverage, which is in essence controlled by the roving dimensions. On the other hand, the number of windings is dictated by the strength of the applied rovings. Therefore these two parameters should match in a single pattern without additional weight (excess windings).

The method presented here is analytical and easy to implement in a standard mathematics software package. Localisation of the optimal set of parameters relies here on the maximisation of the vessel performance, based on roving dimensions that fit into a pattern.

This integral approach leads to some remarkable conclusions. First, the fibres used for the additional hoop layers on the cylindrical part do not always have to be as strong as possible. Second, the utilisation of weaker fibres is in some extreme cases able to reduce weight, particularly when a strong fibre based design leads to impossible patterns or strain mismatch for the dome-cylinder junction.

After a short outline of the role the basic classical lamination theory can play in the shell stress analysis, the dome-cylinder strain matching procedure is shortly explained. Next, the performance parameters of the resulting pressure vessel are linked to the basic design parameters like internal pressure, desired volume and laminate properties. These parameters, in conjunction with the roving dimensions are then formalised as functions that determine possible winding patterns. After a short demonstration of the methodology on a design case, some key conclusions are given.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of a pressure vessel dome

2. SHELL ANALYSIS

2.1. Definitions & notations

Due to several differences in Western / Eastern European and American nomenclature, some definitions are here given [10]:

- $\{1, 2\}$ = material coordinate system of a single layer
- \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{C} = stiffness / compliance matrix of a single orthotropic layer
- $\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ = stress / strain vector of a single layer

- $\{x, y\}$ = coordinate system of the laminate
- $\underline{\mathbf{S}}, \underline{\mathbf{C}}$ = stiffness / compliance matrix of laminate
- $\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ = stress / strain vector of laminate

- $\{\theta, \phi\}$ = shell coordinate system {parallel, meridional}, coincident with $\{x, y\}$

In addition, the contraction ratio follows here the Western definition:

$$\frac{V_{xy}}{E_x} = \frac{V_{yx}}{E_y} \quad (1)$$

where the first subscript denotes the applied stress direction and the second stands for the direction of the generated (transverse) strain.

For the stress / strain transformations we employ here the engineering stress & strain based matrices. The stress transformation matrix is:

$$\mathbf{M}(\alpha) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \alpha & \sin^2 \alpha & \sin(2\alpha) \\ \sin^2 \alpha & \cos^2 \alpha & -\sin(2\alpha) \\ -\cos \alpha \sin \alpha & \cos \alpha \sin \alpha & \cos(2\alpha) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

In a similar fashion, the strain transformation matrix is given by:

$$\mathbf{N}(\alpha) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \alpha & \sin^2 \alpha & \cos \alpha \sin \alpha \\ \sin^2 \alpha & \cos^2 \alpha & -\cos \alpha \sin \alpha \\ -\sin(2\alpha) & \sin(2\alpha) & \cos(2\alpha) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{N}^{-1} = \mathbf{M}^t$.

2.2 Lamination theory

A laminate manufactured by filament winding can be considered as an angle ply [15]. The reduced compliance matrix of a single orthotropic layer is given by [3]:

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_1} & 0 \\ \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The corresponding stiffness matrix \mathbf{S} is obtained by inversion of equation (4). The stiffness matrix of the resulting angle ply laminate becomes (figure 1):

$$\underline{\mathbf{S}} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{S}(\alpha) + \mathbf{S}(-\alpha)) \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{S}(\alpha) = \mathbf{M}(\alpha) \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{M}^T(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

Due to rotational symmetry for the shape and the applied loads (internal pressure and axial loading, figure 1), the shell stresses do not have a shear component hence the applied stress vector is [5]:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{\theta} \\ \sigma_{\phi} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The strains in the main shell direction (θ and ϕ reference system, figure 1) are given by:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \underline{\mathbf{C}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (8)$$

Where $\underline{\mathbf{C}} = \underline{\mathbf{S}}^{-1}$. The strains in a particular layer (with respect to its material axes) are given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\alpha) = \mathbf{N}(\alpha) \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \mathbf{N}(\alpha) \cdot \underline{\mathbf{C}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (9)$$

The corresponding stress vector of a single layer becomes:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\alpha) = \mathbf{S} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\alpha) = \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{N}(\alpha) \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{N}(\alpha) \cdot \underline{\mathbf{C}} \cdot \underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (10)$$

2.3 Optimality conditions

The components of the layer stresses vector form the input parameters for the selected stress-based strength criterion (e.g. Tsai-Hill). Alternatively, one can plug the result of equation (9) into a strain-based criterion. For example, in [16] the authors have employed a conservative version of the Hill criterion:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{S_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{S_2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{T_{12}}\right)^2 \leq 1 \quad (11)$$

where S_1 , S_2 , are the tensile / compressive strength values of a single layer in respectively the “1” and “2” direction (1 is the fibre direction), and T_{12} the in-plane shear strength. Depending on the sign of $\sigma_{\#}$ one should select the appropriate tensile or compressive value for $S_{\#}$. Based on this criterion, Vasiliev, Krikanov and Razin [16] derived the optimality conditions (minimum weight by maximum stored energy) for a pressure vessel by maximizing the stress invariant $\sigma_1 + \sigma_2$ ($=\sigma_{\theta} + \sigma_{\phi}$) under constraint (11). These conditions imply zero shear stress in the participating layers, $\tau_{12} = 0$. The same result, based on the assumption of equal layer strains ($\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_2$) has been derived by de Jong [8]. In this work however, the full form of the Tsai-Hill criterion is employed [3]:

$$\Omega = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{S_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{S_2}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{S_1^2}\right) + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{T_{12}}\right)^2 \leq 1 \quad (12)$$

which is less conservative than (11).

Returning to the zero in-plane shear stress condition, several authors have shown that the shell stress (laminate level) must comply with [10, 16]:

$$\frac{\sigma_{\phi}}{\sigma_{\theta}} = \frac{\sin^2 \alpha + k_e \cos^2 \alpha}{\cos^2 \alpha + k_e \sin^2 \alpha} \quad (13)$$

where [10]:

$$k_e = \frac{E_2(1+\nu_{12})}{E_1(1+\nu_{21})} \quad (14)$$

For maximum strength however (according to criterion (11)), we must replace k_e with k_{σ} , given by [16]:

$$k_{\sigma} = \left(\frac{S_2}{S_1}\right)^2 \quad (15)$$

For the netting case (where the mechanical properties of the matrix are neglected) relations (14) and (15) simplify to $k_e = k_\sigma = 0$. On the other hand, for $k = 1$ the utilised material becomes isotropic. Note that the condition of maximum strength does not automatically imply maximised vessel performance since the employed k value will affect the resulting meridian profile, hence the contained volume of the calculated vessel. From this point we will use the notation k ($0 \leq k \leq 1$) for the anisotropy parameter.

2.4 Dome profiles

Depending on the k parameter, several profiles for the meridian of the optimal dome can be obtained. Before proceeding to the analysis of such profiles we introduce some design parameters and dimensionless variables, figure 1:

- c = polar opening radius [mm]
- ρ = vessel radius [mm]
- z = height coordinate of the meridian profile [mm]
- R = equator radius [mm]
- h = length of cylindrical part [mm]
- P = internal pressure [MPa]
- F_a = external axial force, applied on the polar cap [N]

- Y = ρ / c $Y \geq 1$
- Y_{eq} = R / c $Y_{\text{eq}} \geq 1$
- Z = z / c $Z > 0$
- H = h / c $H \geq 0$
- r = $\frac{F_a}{\pi P R^2}$

In addition, it is assumed here that the vessel is covered by geodesic roving trajectories for which the winding angle α is given by [8, 10, 16]:

$$\alpha = \arcsin\left(\frac{1}{Y}\right) \quad (16)$$

As derived in [10], for a given every $\{Y_{\text{eq}}, r, k\}$ combination, the meridian profile $Z(Y)$ is given by integration of:

$$Z'(Y) = \pm \frac{Y(Y^2 + rY_{\text{eq}}^2)}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{k + Y^2 - 1}{k + Y_{\text{eq}}^2 - 1}\right)^{k+1} (1+r)^2 Y_{\text{eq}}^6 - Y^2 (Y^2 + rY_{\text{eq}}^2)^2}} \quad (17)$$

The integration interval is $[Y_{\min}, Y_{\text{eq}}]$ where Y_{\min} is in general not equal to 1. The denominator of the above given equation might nullify for Y values slightly bigger (in some cases also slightly smaller) than 1 [8, 10], so in practice the aimed aspect ratio R/c might not be exactly achievable. However, the differences are negligibly small. In the calculations presented here, we assume that:

$$Y_{\min} = \max \left\{ Y : \left(\frac{k + Y^2 - 1}{k + Y_{\text{eq}}^2 - 1} \right)^{k+1} (1+r)^2 Y_{\text{eq}}^6 - Y^2 (Y^2 + r Y_{\text{eq}}^2)^2 = 0 \right. \\ \left. 1 \right\} \quad (18)$$

where the root searching interval for Y is $[1, Y_{\text{eq}}/2]$.

In figure 2 we provide various profiles for zero externally applied axial force ($r = 0$) by an aspect ratio (R/c) of approximately 5. The role of the material “anisotropy” parameter k is here clearly visible. For $k=1$ we almost obtain a sphere whereas for $k = 0$ the form becomes a pure netting-based isotensoid.

Fig. 2. Influence of k on the resulting meridian profile ($Y_{\text{eq}} = 5, r = 0$)

2.5 Strain compatibility

Consideration of shell stress equilibrium [baker, flugge], in combination with (18), leads to [Koussios]:

$$\sigma_{\theta}^{(d)} = \left(\frac{Pc}{2t_d} \right) \left(\frac{(1+r)Y_{eq}^3}{Y^2} \right) \left(\frac{k+Y^2-1}{k+Y_{eq}^2-1} \right)^{\frac{k+1}{2}} \quad (19)$$

$$\sigma_{\phi}^{(d)} = \frac{1+k(Y^2-1)}{k+Y^2-1} \sigma_{\theta}^{(d)}$$

where t_d stands for laminate thickness at the dome. With a given $\{Y_{eq}, r, k\}$ vector and known engineering constants for the used material, the shell stresses can be plugged into the strength analysis procedure as outlined in sub-section 2.2. The result is the minimally required laminate thickness for the dome as a function of the Y coordinate:

$$t_d(Y) = \frac{1}{2} Pc \left(\max \left\{ \sqrt{\Omega(\alpha)}, \sqrt{\Omega(-\alpha)} \right\} \right) \Big|_Y \quad (20)$$

where Ω stands for the non-conservative form of the Hill criterion with active equality, equation (12). The subscript 'd' refers to the dome.

Fig. 3. Polar and hoop windings on cylindrical pressure vessel

A similar procedure can be carried out for the cylindrical part of the vessel. As the most important assumption for the strain analysis relies on the absence of bending loads, it is important to ensure deformation compatibility between the cylindrical part and the dome at their junction. For this scope, the cylindrical part has to be covered by additional hoop windings ($\alpha = \pi/2$), distributed over f complete layers (figure 3). The associated stiffness matrix becomes [10]:

$$\underline{\mathbf{S}}_c = \left(\frac{1}{1+f} \right) \underline{\mathbf{S}}_d(Y_{eq}) + \left(\frac{f}{1+f} \right) \underline{\mathbf{S}}(\pi/2) \quad (21)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} t_h &= ft_d(Y_{eq}) \\ t_c &= t_h + t_d(Y_{eq}) \end{aligned} \quad f \in \mathbb{N}^+ \quad (22)$$

The subscript ‘c’ stands for cylinder, ‘h’ for hoop and ‘p’ for polar. The latter refers to the windings originating at the dome and continue over the cylindrical surface with an angle $\alpha(Y_{eq})$, fig. 3. The dome strains at the cylinder dome intersection (Y_{eq}) are:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_d(Y_{eq}) = \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\theta^{(d)}(Y_{eq}) \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\phi^{(d)}(Y_{eq}) \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \underline{\mathbf{C}}_d[\alpha(Y_{eq})] \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\theta^{(d)}(Y_{eq}) \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_\phi^{(d)}(Y_{eq}) \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{Pc}{2t_d(Y_{eq})} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_d[\alpha(Y_{eq})] \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} (1+r)Y_{eq} \\ 1+k(Y_{eq}^2-1) \\ k+Y_{eq}^2-1 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

The cylindrical part is loaded by [8, 10]:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_c = \frac{Pc}{2(t_d(Y_{eq})+t_c)} \begin{Bmatrix} (1+r)Y_{eq} \\ 2Y_{eq} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

which gives:

$$\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_c = \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\theta^{(c)}(Y_{eq}) \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\phi^{(c)}(Y_{eq}) \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{Pc}{2t_d(Y_{eq})(1+f)} \underline{\mathbf{C}}_c \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} (1+r)Y_{eq} \\ 2Y_{eq} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \text{where } \underline{\mathbf{C}}_c = \underline{\mathbf{S}}_c^{-1} \quad (25)$$

For a known $\{Y_{eq}, r\}$ vector, the only way for achieving the same tangential strains in the dome-cylinder intersection relies on two parameters: k and f . The latter is constrained by manufacturing issues; one has to apply an integer number of hoop layers. By regarding f as given, the k -value (k_0) that ensures strain matching is provided by the solution of:

$$k_0(f) = k : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\phi^{(d)}(k) = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_\phi^{(c)}(k, f), \quad f \in \mathbb{N}^+ \quad (26)$$

In practice, consideration of 1 to 4 hoop layers does usually cover the feasible domain for minimum weight design. With the additional hoop layers however, the cylindrical part is in most cases too strong so there is some excess weight. Creating hoop layers with weaker (and probably also lighter) fibres would in this case improve the performance. In addition, k_0 does usually overshadow the profitable effect of the optimal k (k_e for maximum performance or k_σ for maximum strength). In some cases, designing with k_e (without taking care for strain compatibility) might even knock down the performance by a factor 5 [10].

3. VESSEL PROPERTIES

3.1 Definitions

To assess the performance and suitability for production of a particular vessel design, we first introduce some new symbols:

- ϕ : parallel angle of the applied roving, fig. 1. [rad]
- Φ : parallel angle range of a complete winding [rad]
- $\Delta\Phi$: angular difference between two adjacent windings, fig. 4. [rad]
- V : internal volume / c^3
- L : roving length / c
- B : effective roving width / c
- T : effective roving thickness / c
- T_{eq} : $t_d(Y_{eq}) / c$
- δ : density of the laminate (roving + resin) [kg/l]
- g : gravitational constant = 9.81 [m/s²]

The performance is given by [8, 10, 12, 16]:

$$\eta = \frac{PV}{W} \quad [10^3 \text{ m}] \quad (27)$$

where P is the applied pressure [10^6 Nm^{-2}], V the contained volume [-] and W the weight of the vessel per unit volume [10^3 Nm^{-3}].

The applied pressure is given as a design parameter. In addition, we assume that here that the externally applied axial load is equal to zero. To quantify the performance, one has to determine the internal volume and the weight of the laminate. The first unknown parameter is straight forward, but for the calculation of the resulting laminate thickness along the meridian profile (and thereof the volume and weight) we can use several approximation theories [12, 16]. Regardless the method of schematising the thickness distribution, the nature of the winding process dictates that a certain roving length L_{tot} (dimensionless) is to be placed on the mandrel. As this roving passes through the resin bath, a well determined amount of resin is picked up. Therefore we assume here that the laminate weight is simply given by:

$$W = g\delta L_{\text{tot}}BT \quad [10^3 \text{ Nm}^{-3}] \quad (28)$$

where B and T account for the width, respectively thickness of the roving-resin combination (both dimensionless) and δ for the associated combined density (mixture law). Not surprisingly, the result is practically identical to those given by integrating the various in the literature available thickness approximations over the vessel surface [12].

3.2 Dome

As the meridian shape function is known (equation (17)), the ϕ -coordinate of a roving, geodetically placed over the dome surface, becomes [7]:

$$\phi'_d(Y) = \frac{\sqrt{1+Z'^2(Y)}}{Y} \tan \alpha(Y) \quad (29)$$

The ϕ -propagation over a single trajectory (e.g. departing at the equator and arriving at the pole) can be obtained by integration of (29) over the interval $[Y_{\text{eq}}, Y_{\text{min}}]$. As the dome is covered by two of these trajectories (equator→pole→equator) and the vessel has obviously two domes, the total, dome related ϕ -contribution is obtained by multiplying the integration result by 4.

The roving length differential is given by:

$$L'_d(Y) = \frac{\sqrt{1+Z'^2(Y)}}{\cos \alpha(Y)} \quad (30)$$

With a similar reasoning, the total, dome related roving length is 4 times the integral of (30) over $[Y_{\text{eq}}, Y_{\text{min}}]$. The internal volume differential is:

$$V'_d(Y) = \pi Y^2 Z'(Y) \quad (31)$$

Hence the total dome related volume is 2 times the integral of (31) over $[Y_{\text{eq}}, Y_{\text{min}}]$. Note that all quantities presented here are dimensionless.

3.3 Cylindrical part

As the cylindrical part is covered with two roving trajectories (upper dome→lower dome→upper dome, continuation from the dome) with a constant angle $\alpha(Y_{\text{eq}})$ we can simply state that:

$$\Phi_c^{(p)} = 2 \frac{H}{Y_{\text{eq}}} \tan \alpha(Y_{\text{eq}}) \quad (32)$$

where 'p' stands for polar winding. The associated roving length is:

$$L_c^{(p)} = 2 \frac{H}{\cos \alpha(Y_{eq})} \quad (33)$$

The hoop layers result in a laminate thickness as given in equation (22a). The total laminate volume of the hoop layers is $2\pi f Y_{eq} H T_{eq}$, which is equal to $L_c^{(h)} B T$. Hence:

$$L_c^{(h)} = 2\pi f \left(\frac{H}{B} \right) \left(\frac{T_{eq}}{T} \right) \quad (34)$$

The volume contained by the cylindrical part simply is:

$$V_c = \pi Y_{eq}^2 H \quad (35)$$

3.4 Total roving length

Before proceeding to any winding pattern related derivation we emphasize here that the number of hoop windings does not depend on the selected winding pattern. On the other hand, the equatorial dome thickness (related to the polar windings over the cylindrical part) is build up by a certain number of windings that cross the equatorial periphery (n), eventually distributed over more than one layers (d). Therefore we can state that (note that a single winding crosses the equatorial periphery two times):

$$2\pi Y_{eq} T_{eq} = 2 \underbrace{nd}_{\zeta} B_{eq} T \rightarrow \zeta = \pi \left(\frac{Y_{eq}}{B_{eq}} \right) \left(\frac{T_{eq}}{T} \right) \quad (36)$$

where:

$$B_{eq} = \frac{B}{\cos \alpha(Y_{eq})} \quad (37)$$

With the number of windings ζ (also referred to as coverage parameter) given, the total roving length (including the hoop layers) becomes:

$$L_{tot} = \zeta \left(4 \int_{Y_{min}}^{Y_{eq}} L'_d(Y) dY + L_c^{(p)} \right) + L_c^{(h)} \quad (38)$$

In combination with equation (28) one can calculate the weight of the laminate per unit of volume.

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of a winding pattern

4. WINDING PATTERNS

4.1 Principles

The establishment of a winding pattern is shortly illustrated in figure 4 where we present a schematic top view of a vessel. The roving passes the points {A, B, C, D} and restarts a new winding. As depicted here, the periphery gets divided into 14 segments ($p = 14$). In every segment, a number k of roving widths will fit. The total number of windings is nd , where d stands for the number of closed layers placed on each other and n is the number of roving widths that fits into the periphery.

After the 14th winding, the roving returns approximately to the position of winding 1 (15th winding, grey disks in the figure). If “winding 15” would lie exactly above point B, continuation of the winding process would have not been possible. Placement of “15” before B is called leading winding; the opposite case is referred to as lagging winding. In the event we wish to create only one closed layer, the distance between “15” and B should exactly correspond to a single roving bandwidth B_{eq} . In the case where two closed layers are required, this difference should be $0.5B_{eq}$ and so on. A successful winding pattern is captured by [14]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (p+1)kd - nd &= +1 && \text{Leading} \\
 pkd - nd &= -1 && \text{Lagging} \\
 p, k, nd &\in \mathbb{N}^+ &&
 \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

Note that when $d > 1$ n is not necessarily an integer.

4.2 Parameters

The realisation of a pattern is entirely dependent on the angle $\Delta\Phi$, measured on the Y_{eq} -periphery, between two adjacent windings. In figure 4 this would be the angle $\widehat{\text{BE}}$. The unbounded value of this angle is given by:

$$\Phi_{\text{tot}} = \Phi_{\text{c}}^{(p)} + 4 \int_{Y_{\text{min}}}^{Y_{\text{eq}}} \phi'_{\text{d}} dY \quad (40)$$

For pattern determination we use [11]:

$$\Delta\Phi = \min \left\{ \left| \text{mod}_{(2\pi)} (\Phi_{\text{tot}}) \right|, \left| \text{mod}_{(-2\pi)} (\Phi_{\text{tot}}) \right| \right\} \quad (41)$$

In addition, the effective roving width B_{eq} (equation (37)) is converted in:

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{B_{\text{eq}}}{Y_{\text{eq}}} \quad (42)$$

The pattern parameters p and k are defined as [14]:

$$\begin{aligned} p &= \text{IP} \left(\frac{2\pi}{\Delta\Phi} \right) \\ k &= \text{CE} \left(\frac{\Delta\Phi}{\Delta\varphi} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

where IP stands for ‘integer part’ and CE for ‘ceiling’. The last parameter, nd , is the biggest integer containing ζ (equation (36)):

$$nd = \text{CE}(\zeta) \quad (44)$$

Apparently, the coverage parameter is the only link between patterns and compliance with the minimally required thickness T_{eq} .

With the pattern constants given, the angle between two neighbouring windings should satisfy (see also equation (39)) [14]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\Phi_{\text{leading}} &= \left(\frac{2\pi}{p+1} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{\zeta} \right) \\ \Delta\Phi_{\text{lagging}} &= \left(\frac{2\pi}{p} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\zeta} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

4.3 Solution procedure

For a given set of vessel design parameters $\{Y_{eq}, r\}$ and a vector of realistic numbers for the additional hoop layers, e.g. $f = (1, 2, 3, 4)$ a series of $k_0(f)$ values will emerge (equation (26)). Among them, a particular f value in combination with H (given dimensionless cylindrical length) will provide the best performance η (equation (27)). The latter is independent of the selected $\{B, T\}$ so the performance is not affected. After all, we can achieve the same laminate thickness with a big number of narrow/thin rovings or a smaller number of broad/thick fibre bundles without affecting the weight. Having a predetermined range for $\{B, T\}$ (usually given in the form of discrete values due to availability), the first condition that must be satisfied is:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\Phi_{\text{leading}} &= \Delta\Phi_{\text{tot}} \\ \Delta\Phi_{\text{lagging}} &= \Delta\Phi_{\text{tot}}\end{aligned}\tag{46}$$

These relations (if there is a solution within the provided $\{B, T\}$ range) result in a series of:

$$TB = \text{const.}\tag{47}$$

With these expressions, the coverage parameter ζ can be quantified. The resulting nd value(s) (equation (44)) can now be plugged in equation (39) to exactly pinpoint the B -value(s) that satisfies(y), next to the structural requirements, the pattern conditions. The number of feasible patterns depends on the number of feasible solutions for (47).

5. EXAMPLE

In this section we will demonstrate the interaction of strain compatibility, cylindrical length, roving dimensions and patterns. The design parameters are:

- $P = 10$ [MPa]
- $r = 0$ [-]
- $c = 25$ [mm]
- $Y_{eq} = 8$ [-]
- $H = 15$ [-]
- $\{B_{\min}, B_{\max}\} = \{0.1, 0.5\}$ [-]
- $\{f_{\min}, f_{\max}\} = \{1, 5\}$ [-]

Note that c does not influence the performance neither does it have any impact on the winding patterns. As everything here is dimensionless it serves only the purpose of “translating” the design into a real volume. Therefore, every desired volume can be obtained by properly adjusting this parameter. In addition, the roving thickness is here a result so it does not have to be known in a-priori fashion.

The layer properties for the employed laminate are assumed as:

- $E_x = 60000$ [MPa]
- $E_y = 9800$ [MPa]
- $\nu_{xy} = 0.3$ [-]
- $G_{xy} = 3400$ [MPa]
- $S_{1, \text{tension}} = 1500$ [MPa]
- $S_{1, \text{compression}} = -1350$ [MPa]
- $S_{2, \text{tension}} = 40$ [MPa]
- $S_{2, \text{compression}} = -210$ [MPa]
- $T_{12} = 50$ [MPa]

The best performance for this design case (which is independent of B) is achieved for $f = 3$ (equation (27)). A short assessment of equations (40) and (45) leads to the conclusion that there is no lagging pattern able to satisfy relation (46) since the graphs of $\Phi_{\text{tot}}(B)$ and $\Phi_{\text{lagging}}(B)$ do not intersect for $B_{\text{min}} \leq B \leq B_{\text{max}}$. Next, equation (46) dictates that $BT = 0.00508765$. With this relation the ζ parameter becomes equal to 726.168 hence we need $nd = 727$ windings. Dividing this number by $\{[2\pi / \Delta\phi(B_{\text{min}})], [2\pi / \Delta\phi(B_{\text{max}})]\}$ results in $\{2, 8\}$ layers for the polar windings. Therefore, the final value for T is, as expected, directly linked to the number of overwound layers. Substitution of $nd = 727$ into equation (39a) and solving for B gives finally two roving candidates:

- $B = 0.15c$ $T = 0.0339$ $d = 2$ pattern: $26 \times 14 \times 2 - 727 = 1$
- $B = 0.32c$ $T = 0.0159$ $d = 4$ pattern: $26 \times 7 \times 4 - 727 = 1$

With $c = 25$ [mm] this would mean that the suitable roving thicknesses are $\{0.4, 0.84\}$. As a thickness of 0.4 [mm] is more realistic, it is advised to choose here for the second option. It should be noted however that neither the structural performance nor the winding time is affected by this selection.

6. CONSLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented an extensive consideration of the integral optimal design procedure for cylindrical pressure vessels. Starting with the basics of the classical lamination theory, the stress analysis of the anisotropic shell (representing the wall of the pressure vessel) is here performed. Particular emphasis has been given to the problem of strain compatibility for the dome and the cylindrical part. Next, the properties of the designed pressure vessel have been analysed in order to capture the performance parameter. In the subsequent section, associated with the set-up of suitable fibre patterns, it has been shown that the coverage parameter is the most important link between the desired laminate thickness and the winding pattern that has to build up that thickness.

The results clearly indicate that the strain compatibility issue is of significant importance; if a pressure vessel design does not comply with this, structural optimisation in terms of winding angle adaptation or fine-tuning of the laminate properties proves entirely useless. An additional conclusion, triggered by this principle, is that some times a weaker fibre (employed for the additional hoop layers on the cylindrical part) is preferred above the original one that covers the dome. This is rather unexpected; a weaker fibre improves the performance (?) but we must keep in mind that that strain compatibility is a matter of equalising strains and not maximising the stiffness.

The performance of the vessel is shown to depend on the laminate anisotropy parameter, axial loading, aspect ratio of the vessel and the conditions for strain compatibility. The analysis procedure for winding pattern has demonstrated that, as expected, the selection of a particularly-dimensioned roving should not affect the performance as long as it complies with the structural requirements. However, it has been shown that only rovings of a particular thickness (leading to a particular laminate strength in the roving direction) are able to satisfy the pattern conditions. If the combination “roving properties” – “thickness” is based on *B*-values that lie outside the feasibility domain for the associated patterns, the designer must sacrifice the performance by adding a (significant) excess laminate weight.

In more general terms, it can be concluded that the optimisation of pressure vessels cannot solely rely on structural performance issues but has also to take production issues into account like availability of particular rovings / fibre bundles and patterns (that undoubtedly influence the winding time). This integral consideration is in practice not very assessable, but proper parameterisation can lead to straight forward evaluation procedures. We should however emphasize here that the method presented in this paper is not the only possible one. Due to the co-dependency of the involved design parameters (from vessel aspect ratio up to the roving thickness) an alternative calculation flow might be more transparent. An assessment of the best possible way to fully automate the pressure vessel design procedure is part of ongoing research.

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